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African Continental Free Trade Area Agreement and Nigeria's Manufacturing Sector (2018-2022)

Chukwujekwu Lazarus OKAFOR¹ & Prof. Charles Arinze OBIORA²

^{1,2}Department of Political Science,
Faculty of Social Sciences,

Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

African Continental Free Trade Area was lauded by the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa that the agreement will boost intra-African trade by 52 percent by 2022. This notwithstanding, Nigeria dragged foot with signing the agreement expressing worries over the fate of the local manufacturers and entrepreneurs but later signed it anyway. Based on the foregoing, this study investigated the implications of the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) on Nigeria's Manufacturing sector 2019-2022. The study was qualitative in nature as data was gotten from secondary sources of data: textbooks, the internet, library, magazine, newspaper, while the theory of functionalism which is an important component parts of the broad theory of integration were adopted as the frame work of analysis. The study revealed that the Nigeria's low industrial base and the practice of mono-economic system present a serious challenge to its Nigeria's capacity to benefit adequately from the AfCFTA. The study also established that the Nigerian economy is vulnerable to the African Continental Free Trade Area Agreement on free movement of people and goods. The study recommends among other things that: there is need for Nigeria to incorporate the collaboration and initiatives of both the private and public sectors to invest in cross-border infrastructure of the country which will help in closing up Nigeria's physical infrastructure gap which already requires a huge capital investment as well as the revenue losses in smuggling, dumping and illicit trade flows.

Keyword: AfCFTA, Manufacturing Sector, Mono-Economy, Nigeria's Industrialization, ACFTA Agreement

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Nigeria as the largest economy in Africa signed the AfCFTA on July 7, 2019, becoming the 34th member of the trading bloc. Under the AfCFTA, Nigeria stands to gain from increased access to cheaper goods and services from other African countries, as its intra-African trade is currently low: Indeed, as of 2018, Nigeria's imports from the African region relative to total imports was at 3.2 percent while the share of Nigeria's exports to the African region relative to total exports was 13.2 percent. Moreover, in 2020, Nigeria's main trading partner was actually China (Olajide, 2021). Nigeria's hesitation and feet-dragging in committing promptly to the AfCFTA is particularly hinged on the consideration of its peculiar economic realities - including its productive base, industrial capacity, export and import trade relations, and general market conditions. President Muhainmadu Buliari argued that Nigeria will not engage in any free trade agreement that would affect the local manufactures and the upcoming entrepreneurs in the country (Mumbere, 2018). Nigeria had several consultations with the local manufacturers through the Chief Trade Negotiator and Director General, Nigerian Office for Trade Negotiations, Ambassador

Chinedu Osakwe, to ensure their effective involvement towards the take-off of the AfCFTA deal (The Conversation, July 26, 2018). However, the local businesses expressed strong skepticism to buy -in to the AC-FTA deal.

Many trade unions, stakeholders and industrial firms, especially the Nigeria Labour Congress (NLC), opposed Nigeria's endorsement of the AfCFTA Agreement. The NLC stated that it is a "renewed, extremely dangerous and radioactive neo-liberal policy initiative" that will create unsafe and difficult work conditions, increase economic pressure on the workers, and potentially exposing workers to migration to other countries. The Trade unions and manufacturers generally challenge Nigeria's engagement in AfCFTA particularly on the grounds that Nigeria still has low industrial capacity and that local manufacturers are not yet fully developed to withstand the shock of external market competition (Crabtree, 2018). This is because currently, Nigeria's export goods are mainly composed of oil products, with little or no export diversification on non-oil sectors of the economy.

In adoption of AfCFTA by Nigeria, Nigeria was a leader in the negotiations to establish the AfCFTA with Ambassador Chiedu Osakwe as Nigeria's Chief Trade Negotiator, chairing the 55-member Negotiating Forum for the AfCFTA (AfCFTA-NF). Nigeria was deeply committed to the process of negotiating the AfCFTA. The Nigerian Government is taking steps to ensure that the adoption of the AfCFTA is not detrimental to its economy. At the Summit (21st March, 2018), 44 African countries agreed to form a \$3 trillion Continental Free Trade Zone encompassing 1.2 billion people. Nigeria, South Africa, Botswana, Lesotho, Namibia, Zambia, Burundi, Eritrea, Benin, Sierra Leone and Guinea Bissau are the countries that stayed out of the bloc as at the date.

Buttressing the importance of AfCFTA, Andrew Mold, the Acting Director for the ECA in Eastern Africa, has stated that the AfCFTA is a "major milestone towards making the Pan-African aspiration a reality." He further explained that despite the expected losses from tariff revenues for the Continent, which is estimated at about 4 billion USD, the benefits are higher, especially from lower prices for consumer goods. A major concern has been raised by Macleod which is the challenge of implementation. He is of the opinion that AfCFTA implementation Roadmap, including preparing schedules of commitments in goods and services should be completed first.

Statement of Problem

Generally, most scholars affirm that the AfCFTA deal will provide strong measures for effective liberalization of trade and reduce trade costs in order to give consumers the opportunity to have access to more products at affordable prices within the African sub-region. It is believed that primary products and raw materials that are imported and other intermediate inputs will enhance competitive trade among local manufacturers and promote economic value chain on the continent.

Nigeria is widely perceived at the global stage as a protectionist country, owing to its weak industrial base, low productive capacity and infant manufacturing sector that cannot survive stiff competition at the continental and global markets. There are also serious concerns regarding Nigeria's over-concentration on oil exports with less diversification of non-oil exports.

Other problems are; Deficiency in the human and technological capacity of SMEs making them vulnerable to larger firms; Limited access to SME finance and trade finance/high cost of capital; Poor/limited access to good infrastructures like steady power supply, good road network and transport system, and digital infrastructure; Foreign suppliers dominating the market making the local producers lose out; and Loss of intellectual property to larger corporations due to poorly enforced patent laws.

Based on the foregoing, the following research questions were raised:

1. What were the effects of the African continental free trade area agreement on the manufacturing sector of the Nigerian Economy between 2018-2022?
2. What factors undermined Nigeria's capacity to benefit from the African Continental Free Trade Area Agreement between 2018-2022?

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to examine the African continental free trade area agreement and Nigeria's manufacturing sector (2018-2022). However, the specific objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To identify the effects of the African continental free trade area agreement on the manufacturing sector of the Nigerian Economy between 2018-2022.
2. To ascertain the factors that undermined Nigeria's capacity to benefit from the African Continental Free Trade Area Agreement between 2018-2022.

2.0 Literature Review

Conceptual Review

The African Continental Free Trade Area Agreement

Proponents of the FTA expect the AfCFTA to reduce poverty, increase firm competitiveness, and boost intra-African trade and investment. In fact, based on a recent survey of 1,804 Nigerian manufacturing enterprises, 6 out of 10 businesses expect the AfCFTA to lead to a reduction in material and labor costs, increase production capacity, expand market and consumer size, and reduce prices. Overall, Nigeria's small and medium-sized businesses are optimistic about the opportunities created by AfCFTA, although with mixed feelings grounded in concerns about rising foreign competition and dumping of substandard goods (Olajide, 2021).

The AfCFTA has key objectives of creating a single continental market for goods and services, with free movement of people and investments. This is expected to promote the creation of a Custom Union. It aims to boost intra-African trade by accelerating strong harmonization and coordination of trade liberalization and economic policies across the various African states, and particularly among the various Regional Economic Communities (RECs). By so doing AfCFTA will encourage competitive trade both in terms of investment and human enterprise especially by exploiting vast opportunities for industrial production, continental market access and efficient management of state resources (Tralac, 2019). However, the general aims and objectives of the AfCFTA Agreement are as follows:

- To establish a single market to enhance economic integration on the African continent
- To liberalize African markets through mutual-benefiting negotiating rounds
- Promote free movement of people, trade and investment capitals within the African sub-region
- Facilitate the creation of a custom union through economic integration
- Achieve inclusive and sustainable economic growth and development, gender equality and structural transformations across African states, etc.

Benefits and Challenges of African Continental Free Trade Area Agreement Nigeria's Industrial Base and Mono-Economy

The effects of AfCFTA on Nigeria's industrial economy are yet to be fully articulated and critically evaluated. It is not yet clear how the AfCFTA Agreement will affect Nigeria's mostly low-level manufacturers, and emerging entrepreneurs and small scale business men and women who are not capitally competent enough and lack productive capacities to withstand regional market competition that would arise from the AfCFTA Agreement. Africa Renewal (2018) observes that most traders and business men and women are enthusiastic about the free trade policy as it affects the export of their locally manufactured goods but are quite afraid at what would happen at the long-term in terms of being able to face the stiff competition that would arise. Although some manufacturers have already expressed satisfaction that they now find it easier to take delivery of some products they use in their local production and services at cheaper rate.

It is observed that the AfCFTA agreement will however take care of the fears of countries regarding multilevel membership in other regional economic communities, which may complicate or affect the general objective of a single, harmonized, free trade market system in the region. This is because any of such multiple involvement in regional economic communities by AfCFTA countries will undermine the operation of the AfCFTA from the start. The general idea therefore is that the AfCFTA Agreement has potentials to transform Africa economically and bring forth economic growth and development but the challenge of achieving effective implementation remains a serious concern and such become the possible weakness of the agreement. The need for a free trade area cannot be over-emphasized, however, there is need to apply strong political will by the African Union and individual member states participating in the

agreement in order to achieve the goals of the agreement, including economic integration in the region (Africa Renewal, 2018).

However, the gains of AfCFTA agreement may not be visible at hand for a number of reasons. First is that: the African Union, an umbrella body that is vested with the responsibility of overseeing the operation and implementation of the AfCFTA, does not yet have any observer status in the World Trade Organization (WTO), even though some attempts have been made towards that but all to no avail. Currently, Africa has a very little percentage - about 3 percent share of world trade, and this unwelcome development has been linked to its protectionist tendencies on imported products and this continues to make African economics vulnerable to external shocks. The intra-trade in Africa has remained far lower than what obtains in other regions of the world, with mini-African trade rates at just 18 percent of all exports. The AfCFTA serves as a weapon to dismantle the inequality existing in global investment relations; so that Africa will no longer remain at the wayside. This will offer very great long-term gains (Chatham House, 2019).

Although the report of Chatham House (2019), observes that a lot of efforts are still needed in order to fully benefit from the estimated gains of the AfCFTA agreement. Among other things the required infrastructures and facilities are still lacking in most African countries and such are highly important for the expected massive investment that will occur as a result of the AfCFTA programme. The challenge is that leaders of African countries are yet to fully make the agreement their economic priorities and consensus on its implementation must be established by the member states if any meaningful progress will be achieved. More disturbing is the fact that the gains of the agreement will be likely uneven and unequally distributed among the participating countries likewise the benefits, so you may always depend on the level of productive capacity of individual countries and their business status.

ACFTA Protocol on Free Movement of People and Goods

Van der Nest (2019), argues that intra-movement (including goods) and migration of people in the region are already predominant and substantial. Van der Nest (2019) further makes a case that most African countries have already put adequate measures together toward implementing free movement of people and goods on the continent and that the success recorded so far would make it less difficult for the AfCFTA Agreement on the same agenda to succeed. However, with the free trade area, it becomes difficult for African states to control its borders and enforce effective controls on external customs.

Stuart (2019b) investigates the level of illicit flow of finance in Africa, which average about 25% of the developing country trade in the last decade. The poor level of border governance and security encourage large flows of illicit trade within the African boundaries. Hence, for African nations to make real economic progress it will have to ensure effective border control and governance to curtail the flow of illegal goods and commodities across the boundaries. The need for export specialization according to different country categorizations will help to understand the nature of illegal crossing of goods across different national borders. African nations can still diversify their economies in two different categories of export specialization such as extractive commodity exporters (including fuels, minerals, and metals) and residual/agricultural exporters.

World Economic Forum on Africa (2019) maintains that the objective of the AfCFTA is to establish a common market system in the African region to benefit the countries therein numbering about 54 states. The main idea according to the report is to promote free movement of people and goods across the states, particularly, business operators and travelers who invest in other countries, so as to develop a custom union on the continent. 'A fully operational custom union in African region will greatly boost trade and investment in the region at the long-run. There will also be job opportunities for the 1.27 billion people that make up Africa. Hence, Nigeria's involvement in the AfCFTA is seen as a welcome development.

Nigeria's Manufacturing Sector and the African Continental Free Trade Agreement

Nigeria is one of the largest economies in Africa with a population of over 200 million people, constituting almost 20% of the total African population (Eke, 2021). As reported by the African Development Bank (2021), Nigeria recorded a -3% growth due to the recession occasioned by the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. Being a middle-income economy and one that thrives and depends majorly on the oil sector (NESG, 2019), oil has become the main source of foreign exchange earnings and

government financing. Oil constitutes 80% of revenue and 95% of export earnings, 83% of Federal Government revenue and 65% of government budgetary revenues and 95% of foreign exchange earnings (CBN, 2010). Nigeria is termed as a net importing country concerning non-oil industrial goods and by implication, Nigeria earns substantially from tariffs paid by importers. The revenue of over ₦400 billion recorded by the Nigerian Customs Services in 2019, gives credence to this assertion (Eke, 2021).

Nigeria recorded a total trade of ₦32.42 trn in 2020 which is 10.3% less than the value recorded in 2019 (₦36.15trn). This translates to a deficit of ₦7.37trn as against a surplus of ₦2.23trn in 2019. The total export stood at ₦12.5trn which was 34.8% lesser than the export value in 2019 whereas, the total import stood at ₦19.9trn, 17.3% higher than the import value in 2019 (NBS, 2021).

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Apart from signing and ratifying the AfCFTA, it is pertinent to note that the Nigerian government has shown commitment towards its success by way of policy formulation. Oyedele (2020) outlined these measures as follows:

- The ***National Action Committee (NAC)*** for the implementation of the AfCFTA which was established by the President, Muhammadu Buhari on the 28th of July, 2019. The committee, which is chaired by the Hon. Minister of Industry, Trade and Investment, is comprised of representatives of Ministries, Departments and Agencies, and selected stakeholder groups from the private sector and the civil society to coordinate the implementation of all the AfCFTA readiness interventions.
- The ***Finance Act*** was signed by the President on the 13th of January, 2020. The Act, which contains tax reliefs especially for micro, small and medium enterprises, is meant to attract investors, promote ease of doing business and accelerate activities promoting economic growth and development in Nigeria.
- The ***New Visa Policy*** allows for citizens of other African countries to be issued a visa on arrival in Nigeria as against having to apply for a Nigerian visa in their respective countries. This visa policy, which was launched on the 4th of February, 2020, was in a bid to promote trade within the African continent and ensure the success of the AfCFTA.

In addition, the Federal Government through the Nigerian Office for Trade Negotiations (NOTN), has outlined measures that exporters that want to take advantage of the AfCFTA should follow. This move followed the kick-off of actual trading under the AfCFTA agreement on 1st January 2021 (Olisah, 2021). The measures are as follows:

Exporter or agent must secure all necessary licenses, permits, certificates and necessary documents from relevant agencies like Nigerian Export Promotion Council (NEPC), Standard Organization of Nigeria (SON), National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC), Nigerian Agricultural Quarantine Service (NAQS) and others.

- Ensure that the product qualifies for export under AfCFTA.
- Next, create a bill of entry, attach all relevant permits from government agencies and secure reservation with shipping or Airline Company. Apply for the Nigerian Customs Service AfCFTA Certificate of Origin after paying a fee.
- The Nigerian Customs Service is the issuer of the certificate, however, the Nigerian Association of Chambers of Commerce, Industry, Mines, and Agriculture (NACCIMA) must vet the application.

- Also, other accompanying documents required for shipment under AfCFTA should be included like Certificate of origin, Nigerian Customs Bill of Entry, Bill of Lading, Packing List, and Certificate of Analysis.

The compulsory documents for AfCFTA trading are Supplier/Producer's declaration form, Origin of declaration form and AfCFTA Certificate of origin.

Empirical Review

Olagunju (2021) examines Nigeria's restrictive trade policies (import and export restrictions) and protectionism and discovers it to be an impeding factor. Arbitrary border closures and import bans on certain goods from other African countries negates the idea of free trade. The closure of the Nigerian-Benin border in 1984-1986, 1996, 2003; the import ban on 100 Ghanaian items in 2003 and the border closure in 2019 (of which 4 of the borders were opened in December 2020) are good instances. Up to 26 goods are prohibited from being imported into the country (FGN Single Window Trade, n.d)

Odiije (2019) examines the value of intra-manufacturing in Africa and finds that the volume of import trade and export trade among African nations totaled about 16.6 percent of the total African exports in 2017. Comparatively, intra-export trade in Europe was 68.1 percent, in Asia it was 59.4% percent while in America it was 55 percent. However, it was noted that the free trade agreement would likely deny the participating states the right to operate some internal economic policies that will protect the local industries and manufacturing firms.

Dr. Kituyi (2019) examined Africa's Phenomenal for Intra-Continental Trade as a clear determination to expand trade among ourselves is an important step. Uncertainties in international trade increase the premium on regional intra-African trade. Secondly, what Nigeria have learned from the rest of the world is that even if there is populist protectionism, it is a short-term phase that we'll ride out. But for Africa to learn from the experience of East Asia and Latin America even as Nigeria wait for protectionism to end, she must build productive trading capacities through regional value chains. Africa trading among its component states strengthens its ability to trade.

Theoretical Review

This study based on the theories of Functionalism and neofunctionalism which are important component parts of the broad theories of integration and Heckscher-Ohlin Theory on Factor-Prices

The theory of functionalism will be built upon the unified goal and needs shared by countries, including non-state entities and actors, in the course of global integration. The key proponents of the functional approach of integration are Mitrany (1933), Ernest B. Haab (1964), Held (1996), Scholte (1993), Rosamond (2000) etc. The Functional theory of integration is fundamentally built from the liberal and idealist ideologies which derived mainly from Emmanuel Kant and Woodrow Wilson (Rosamond, 2000). The functional theory is developed in the pattern of authority based on functions and needs of states, scientific knowledge, technological development, and the idea or structure of a supra-territorial authority.

The theory of functionalism proposes the system of international or regional integration based on the collective governance and 'material interdependence (Mitrany, 1933:101) among states. This informs a level of internal economic structures in states that integrate in limited functional, technical, and/or economic areas. In this function, the international organizations are expected to accomplish important human needs, aided by technology and expertise. The gains provided by the functional organizations would attract the loyalty of the populations and stimulate their involvement and broaden the levels of integration (Scholte, 1993; Held, 1996).

Key assumptions that functionalism proposed include the following:

- (1) That the process of integration occurs in the context of human freedom
- (2) That knowledge and skill are now available to fulfill the needs that the functional organizations are made to fulfill
- (3) That countries should not undermine the process of integration (Rosamond, 2000).

Further, the functionalist approach to international integration has been improved in the form of neofunctionalism which reemphasized the dimension and role of the state in the functional theory and

deemphasized the global aspect. Particularly, Neofunctionalism proposed the idea of regional integration which is mainly derived from the work of David Mitrany. Neofunctionalism critically addressed the immediate process of integration among the state especially within the broad spectrum of regional integration. It was observed that initially the states pursue or have integration in limited functional or economic spheres. Although partially integrated countries connect to increasing levels of integration in related aspects. The product of integration is regarded as 'spill over' by the neofunctionalists. This 'spill over' can occur in two dimensions: functional and political. While functional spillover deals with the inter-linkages of various economic sectors and aspects, including integration in one policy aspect spilling across into others; the political spillover deals with the establishment of supranational governance machinery such as the EU and African Union to supervise the process of integration at the regional level and how states are complying in line with specified policy areas of the integration agreements (Rosamond, 2000; Caporaso, 1998). However, the weakness of the functional and neofunctional theories of integration is that it conceptualized integration as a linear process which made it impossible to make some explanation over some of the setbacks that are inevitable in the process of regional integration.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research will be based on *ex-post facto* research design which is a method of presenting likely antecedents of events that have happened and cannot, therefore, engineered or manipulated by the investigator (Cooper and Schmdier, 2001). In *ex-post facto* research design, researchers rely on what has happened or what is happening by holding some factors constant by careful attention to the sampling. Using time series version of *ex-post facto* research design in testing hypotheses. This study based on qualitative data collection method and rely on secondary sources of data which involve the collection of documentary evidence, written descriptions and official reports. This study adopted the qualitative descriptive method of data analysis.

Hypotheses

This study is based on the following hypotheses stated below:

1. The African Continental Free Trade Area Agreement has an adverse effect on the manufacturing sector of the Nigerian Economy between 2018-2022.
2. Nigeria's low industrial base and mono-economy undermined its capacity to benefit adequately from the African Continental Free Trade Area Agreement between 2018-2022.

4.0 ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Nigeria's Industrialization, Mono-economy and Prospects of the African Continental Free Trade Area Agreement

The AfCFTA deal is positioned as a framework that will create the goal of regional integration on the African continent. The purposes of AfCFTA in relation to the pursuit of regional integration are contained in Article 3 of the AfCFTA agreement which stipulates the broad goals of the agreement as follows: create a single market for goods and services, promoted by the movement of people to deepen the economic integration of the African continent, and in accordance with the pan-African vision of "an integrated, prosperous and peaceful Africa" enshrined in Agenda 2063; create a liberalized market for goods and services through successive rounds of negotiations; devote to the movement of capital and natural people and facilitate investments building on the initiatives and developments in the state parties and regional economic communities (RECs).

The implementation phase of the AfCFTA was launched during AU's 12th Extraordinary Session of the Assembly on 7 July 2019. Nigeria has fully signed and ratified the AfCFA agreement; however, while there are enormous expectations that Nigeria's commitment to the AfCFTA agreement will result to economic growth and prosperity, there are still great concerns whether Nigeria's present economy is well positioned to reap the benefits of the AfCFTA. A GDP of US\$376.284 billion, Nigeria is weighed the largest economy in Africa. It is followed by South Africa (US\$349.299 billion) and Egypt (US\$237.037 billion).²³ with a population of about 200 million, Nigeria is also Africa's largest market. Nigeria's

accession to the treaty is therefore seen as a major boost to the AfCFTA's viability (Onwuka and Udegbonama, 2019).

Nigeria's Problem of Low Industrialization and prospects of the ACFTA Agreement

Maximizing the benefit of any continental free trade area agreement lies in the level of industrial and manufacturing capacities of the relevant countries (Artuc, Lederman, and Porto, 2013). Cazares (2018) noted that the AfCFTA has strong prospects for offering opportunities for economic growth in Africa and susiaina development. However, this will largely depend on the industrial capacity of the individual countries involved. Counties that do not already have fairly enveloped agricultural, industrial and manufacturing sectors may have to incur some long-term negative growth rate based on their AfCFTA agreement commitments. In essence, the gains of having a common market and economic integration, (hjlud.ir.tg gains of welfare from low prices of products, productive efficiency and rise in exports and value-added jobs as well as technological improvements and product specialization), will all depend heavily on the ability of AfCFTA countries to capitalize on well-developed industrial sectors for long-term sustainable economic growth (Kituyi, 2016). On the other hand, low industrial base will result to loss of trade revenue, elimination of local SMEs who cannot face stiffer competition from the AfCFTA free trade area, adjusting unemployment etc). This therefore shows the need for massive investment in infrastructure for industrial stimulation and growth of a wide range of businesses.

Table 2. Selected Indicator Comparative Table

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
Welfare (billion USD)	16.1	10.7
G.D.P growth rate (percent)	0.97	0.66
Employment growth rate (GDP weighted, percent)	1.17	0/82
Intra-African exports (billion USD)	68.0	63.6
Change in intra-African exports (billion USD)	16.8	12.4
Change in intra-Africa exports (percent)	32.8	24.2
Change in total exports (billion USD)	13.5	10.0
Change in total exports (percent)	2.5	1.9
Change in total imports (billion USD)	9.7	9.7
Change in total imports (percent)	1.8	1.8
Trade deficit(billion USD)	3.7	7.2
Trade deficit (percent change)	-50.9	-3.8
Tariff revenue loss(billion USD)	4.1	3.2
Tariff revenue loss from intra-African trade (billion USD)	3.1	2.3
Tariff revenue change (percent)	-9/1	-7.2

Source: GTAP estimates

The above table is quite illustrative as it depicts the long-term changes and cost of the implementation of AfCFTA Agreement on free trade and proposed near-total 90 percent tariff elimination in intra-African trade. The implication is that only insignificant economic progress will be achieved and this is as a result of the poor industrial capacity and lack of adequate trade arid investment diversification among African countries. For example, the table shows that AtCFTA will only record only about 0.97 percent of upward increase in GDP growth rate annually within the first phase of its implementation.

Figure 4. Africa's GDP weighted employment growth by sub-sector (Full FTA, per cent)

Source: GTAP estimates.

The table above clearly depicts the estimated trend of AfCFTA agreement's infinitesimal and insignificant growth rates on employment according to different sub-sectors of African economies. The variety gains according to sub-sectors show that there will be high level of unequal gains and benefits in AfCFTA. The insignificant gains will still not be for every country as some countries whose industrial capacities and export diversification have relatively developed will stand to benefit more while some other countries such as Nigeria that still grapple with low industrial capacities and weak manufacturing sector (due to lack of social infrastructure and excessive high cost of doing business - which frustrates the business environment - with investment denials) will definitely struggle to benefit from the AfCFTA at the short-run but will definitely enter a negative growth level in terms of employment creation and general economic growth at the long-run (Kituyi, 2016). The figure below show the GDP estimates and the distribution of percentage change in trade revenues.

Figure 5. Distribution of GDP growth (Full and SPC tariff cuts)

Source: GTAP estimates.

Figure 6. Distribution of percentage change in tariff revenues (Full and SPC tariff cuts)

Source: GTAP estimates.

The table illustrates the different stages of tax revenue cuts and losses that will occur during the implementation stage of AfCFTA - which will be borne mostly by countries such as Nigeria that have undiversified low industrial and weak manufacturing sector that cannot compete effectively on diversified intra-Africa export trade. The implementation of the AfCFTA agreement will therefore result to uncontrollable revenue losses and negative growth rate in different stages and phases accordingly. This as shown in the table includes -25%; -20% to -24.99%; -15% to -19.99%; -10% to -14.99%; -5% to -9.99%; 0% to 4.99% and +0% respectively. Thus therefore shows that the implementation of AfCFTA have severe revenue losses which will be suffered by low-industrial countries like Nigeria, while diversified export-countries may record only but insignificant gains.

Figure 2. Share of medium and high technology manufactures in African countries' exports to Africa, developed countries and the world (per cent). 2015

Source: UNCTADStat accessed on 18 November 2016. *Lall classification is used.

This above table shows those AfCFTA countries such as South Africa, Kenya, Morocco, Ethiopia, and Egypt, with relatively improved and developed industrial and manufacturing sectors - with the required industrial, social and productive infrastructure will gain more favourably from the benefits of AfCFTA than others including Nigeria that do not have such improved industrial and manufacturing sectors required for diversified export intra-Africa trade (Saygili, Peters, and Knebel, 2018).

Table 3: African Countries Export-Specialization Category Based on Trade Map 2018

S/N	Country	Main Export Category	Export Share of Primary Commodities
1	Algeria	Fuels	98%
2	Angola	Fuels	98%
3	Benin	Agri	82%
4	Botswana	Mining	95%
5	Burkina Faso	Mining	88%
6	Burundi	Agri	77%
7	Cape Verde	Agri	87%
8	Cameroon	Fuels	90%
9	Central African Republic	Agri	93%
10	Chad	Fuels	98%
11	Comoros	Diversified	60%
12	Congo	Fuels	92%

13	Cote d'Ivoire	Agri	79%
14	DRC	Mining	92%
15	Djibouti	Diversified	N/A
16	Egypt	Diversified	46%
17	Equatorial Guinea	Fuels	98%
18	Eritrea	Agri	N/A
19	Ethiopia	Agri	90%
20	Gabon	Fuels	90%
21	Gambia	Agri	55%
22	Ghana	Diversified	80%
23	Guinea	Mining	93%
24	Guinea-Bissau	Agri	98%
25	Kenya	Agri	62%
26	Lesotho	Diversified	35%
27	Liberia	Diversified	64%
28	Libya	Fuels	96%
29	Madagascar	Diversified	67%
30	Malawi	Agri	90%
31	Mali	Mining	77%
12	Mauritania	Mining	98%
33	Mauritius	Diversified	35%
34	Morocco	Diversified	33%
35	Mozambique	Diversified	84%
36	Namibia	Diversified	55%
37	Niger	Diversified	86%
38	Nigeria	Fuels	94%

39	Rwanda	Mining	88%
30	Sao Tome and Principe	Agri	95%
41	Senegal	Diversified	65%
42	Seychelles	Agri	37%
43	Sierra-Leone	Mining	86%
44	Somalia	Agri	90%
45	South Africa	Diversified	48%
46	South Sudan	NA	NA
47	Sudan	Fuels	97%
48	Swaziland	Agri	40%
49	Tanzania	Diversified	70%
50	Togo	Diversified	35%
51	Tunisia	Diversified	27%
52	Uganda	Agri	74%
53	Western Sahara	NA	NA
54	Zambia	Mining	88%
55	Zimbabwe	Diversified	72%
Total Africa Average			77%
Fuels			95%
Milling			89%
Agri			77%
Diversified			57%

Note: Diversified applies to countries with less than 45% of a specific export-specialization based on UNCTAD.
 Source: Stuart, J. (2019) "Export Diversification in Africa and Sustainable Growth." Tralac Working Paper No, US 19WPO2/2019. Stellenbosch:Tralac.

The table above shows that Nigeria's Manufacturing Sector is not diversified with as much as 94% of oil export-specialization. This suggests that Nigeria is a mono-cultural oil-export dependent country. It is very unfortunate that some smaller countries and Nigerian neighbours have attained a high level of export-diversification such as Niger - 86% and Ghana - 80%. Other African countries that have made

outstanding marks in the area of export-trade diversification include Mozambique - 84%; Madagascar - 67%, and Liberia - 64% among others. The implication is that only those countries that have attained appreciable level of export-trade diversification will benefit substantially and maximize the gains of AfCFTA agreement.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the empirical analysis made in the study, it has been established that the Nigeria's low industrial base and operation of a mono-economic system of economy with low export diversification undermine its capacity to benefit significantly from the African Continental Free Trade Area Agreement. This is mainly because Nigeria that has not been able to interlink its various economic sub-sectors and aspects in order to attain backward and forward linkages that would enable its economic diversity export trade; Nigeria's Manufacturing Sector is not diversified with as much as 94% of oil export-specialization. This suggests that Nigeria is a mono-cultural oil-export dependent country.

Base on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. There is need for the Nigerian government to comply with AFCFTA agreements to boost inter-African trade.
2. Nigeria must work hard to boost its ailing manufacturing sector so that she can compete with other African states in trade terms.
3. There is need for the Nigerian government 10 set up measures that can fix the problems of trade disputes among member states for easy and smooth transactions.
4. There is need for Nigerian government to incorporate the collaboration and initiatives of both the private and public sectors to invest in cross-border infrastructure of the economy and also make serious efforts at diversifying her economy.

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